

INFLUENCE OF SURFACE TREATMENT ON THE DYNAMIC-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NATURAL FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

Jochen Gassan and Andrzej K. Bledzki

*Universität Kassel, Institut für Werkstofftechnik - Kunststoff-und Recyclingtechnik
Mönchebergstraße 3, 34109 Kassel, Germany*

SUMMARY: This paper presents investigations concerning the effectiveness of MAH-PP copolymers as coupling agents in jute-polypropylene composites. The cyclic-dynamic values, gained at the load increasing test, pointed out, that the coupling agent reduces the progress in damage at higher limit stresses. Dynamic strength of the MAH-PP modified composites is therefore raised for about 40%. SEM investigations allow to explain the increase of the characteristic values by an improved fiber-matrix adhesion, a less inclination to fiber pull-outs was determined. The improved fiber-matrix adhesion led to a decrease in impact damping-index and loss-energy.

INTRODUCTION

Natural fiber composites combine good mechanical properties with a low specific mass. But, the high level of moisture absorption by natural fibers, their poor wettability, and the insufficient adhesion between untreated fibers and the polymeric matrix, leads to debonding with age [1,4,6].

In all cases, cellulose is the main component of vegetable fibers (at jute approximately 64 wt.-%) [7]. The elementary unit of a cellulose macromolecule is anhydro-d-glucose, which contains three hydroxyls (-OH). These hydroxyls form hydrogen bonds inside the macromolecule itself (intramolecular) and between other cellulose macromolecules (intermolecular) as well as with hydroxyl groups from moist air. Therefore, all vegetable fibers are hydrophilic in nature, and their moisture content can reach 3-13 % [2].

To improve the properties of the composites the reinforcing natural fibers can be modified by physical and chemical methods. Physical methods, such as stretching [17], calendering [18,19], thermotreatment [20], and the production of hybrid yarns [21,22] do not change the chemical composition or structural and surfacial properties of the fiber.

The most important chemical modification methods are the chemical coupling methods. The coupling agent used hereby contain chemical groups, where the one can react with the fiber and the other with the polymer. The formed bonds are covalent and hydrogen bonds as well,

they improve the interfacial adhesion. Graft copolymerizates [15,16] are common methods used for natural fiber reinforcing plastics and will be described in this article. Of common usage is also the treatment with compounds which contain methylol groups [22,23], the treatment with isocyanates [8,9], triazine [6,11] or organosilanes [1,5,12] as coupling agents.

Sterzynski et al. [24] used dimethylurea (in aqueous and methanolic solutions) as coupling agent for injection molded flax-iPP composites. This treatment caused, up to a dimethylurea concentration of 12 wt.-% an 25%-increase of tensile strength and a 20%-increase of Young's modulus. Simultaneously, water repellency was improved.

Other important coupling agents for polypropylenes are silanes. The application of alkylfunctionalized silanes, according to Mieck et al. [25], does not lead to chemical bonds between the cellulose fibers and the PP-matrix. But, it seems to be realistic to assume that the long hydrocarbon chains, provided by the silane application influence the water household and wettability of the fibers and that the chemical affinity to the PP is improved.

Hydrogen bonds as well as covalent bonding mechanisms can be found in the flax-silane system. By this, Mieck et al. [25] found an 60%-increase of shear strength, using a methanolic solution of vinyltrimethoxysilane (dibutylic dilaurat of tin was added as catalyzer), depending on the silane concentration and on the type of catalyzer.

Kokta et al. [16] investigated the influence of different silane types (3% by weight of the fiber) and polymethylene polyphenylisocyanate (PMPPIC, 1% by weight of polymer) on the mechanical properties of wood pulp filled polypropylene. The strength of the silane modified composites was not changed appreciatively. Whereas, the treatment with PMPPIC led to increased strength and stiffness values, caused by chemical bonds between the isocyanate and the hydroxyl groups of the wood fiber surface.

A lot of publications [27-30] are concerned with the effectiveness of MAH-PP copolymers as coupling agent. Mieck et al. [27] determined an increased shear and tensile strength for about 100% respectively 25% at flax-polypropylene composites, whereby the coupling agent was applied on the flax-fibers before the composite was processed. These raised values are dependend on the grafting rate and on the average molar mass of the graftcopolymer.

Similarly increasing values could be attained with PP as matrix material modified with MAH. The acidic anhydride groups of the MAH-PP coupling agent are able to built both, hydrogen- as well as chemical bonds with the hydroxyl group of the flax fiber, wherby a tight anchoring of the coupling agent on the fiber surface is achieved. Besides, the long PP-chains of the MAH-PP coupling agent lead to an adaptation of the very different surface energies of matrix and reinforcement fiber, which allows a good wetting of the fiber for viscous polymers. Again an improved wetting can increase adhesion strength by an increased work of adhesion.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) investigations on MAH-PP modified cellulose fibers (filter paper) proved, according to Felix et al. [29], that this treatment improves wetting, what results in an improved fiber-PP-matrix adhesion compared to unmodified fiber matrix systems. An increase of the composite strength with increasing cellulose content was achieved, similar to Karmaker et al. [30] by the covalent bonds, which were introduced by the addition of a coupling agent.

Similarly improved mechanical properties (tensile- and impact properties) were determined by Avella et al. [28] at MAH-modified iPP composites reinforced with wheat straw fibers. The occuring reduction of moisture uptake was explained by covalent bonds between molecules of acidic maleic anhydride and the fibers.

The chemical bondings between the anhydride- and the hydroxyl groups cause a better force transfer from the matrix into the fibers, which leads to a higher tensile strength [30]. Karmaker et al. [30] determined an increasing composite strength with increasing fiber content when only the MAH-PP coupling agent was used to reinforce jute-PP (average fiber length = 2mm).

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Materials

The tested composites were made of tossa jute-fibers ($n_g = 2$ - woven from J. Schilgen GmbH & Co.) with a fineness of about 280 tex, which were embedded in an PP-Matrix from Vestolen GmbH Germany (Vestolen[®] P 6000F-Table 1) by using the film stacking technique.

Table 1: Technical specification of Vestolen[®] P 6000F - homopolymer³

Characteristic Value	Value
Viscosity	240 cm ³ /g
Melting Flow Index - MVR/230/2.16	7.4 cm ³ /10 min.
Melting Point	164 - 168 °C
Young's Modulus	1500 N/mm ²
Shear Modulus	800 N/mm ²
Vicat Softening Temperature	90°C

To gain a higher fiber matrix adhesion, a fiber modification with MAH-PP (®Hostaprim HC 5 from Hoechst, Germany) was applied. For this procedure the fibers first, had to be dewaxed in an alcoholic solution for 24 hours, removing the woving size (potatoe starch and waxes), subsequently the fibers were washed with distillized water. The following MAH-PP treatment similarly was carried out in an alcoholic solution. The fiber treatment was finished with a 2-hours drying process in a vacuum oven at 75°C.

Mechanical Tests

To determine the influence of the MAH-PP-coupling agent on the mechanical composite properties, the quasi-static flexural test DIN EN 63 (test speed = 2 mm/min) was used. Ten samples were investigated for each case with an standard deviation < 10%.

The load increasing fatigue tests were carried out in accordance to DIN 50 100. At the Institut für Werkstofftechnik a dynamic material testing system, called InDyMat (Intelligent Dynamic

Material Testing) was developed [31]. This system is especially qualified to be used for visco-elastic materials, because the system provides additional informations about damping, dynamic modulus and the cumulated loss-energy (according to Lazan`s definition [32]) of the material. Due to the visco-elastic behaviour of natural fiber composites, a phase shift occurs between applied stress and the material extension.

A sinus-shaped stimulation of the sample, e.g. with a hydropulser, results in a sinus-shaped extension of the sample. The two sinus curves are then separated by a phase angle from each other. Overlaying the two measured signals in a load-extension diagram, results in a hysteresis loop. InDyMat, the computer program, records the hysteresis loop at certain intervals (approximately 1000 values each time) and evaluates them.

The load increasing fatigue tests were carried out as repeated tensile stress tests, with 4 samples (geometry: $120 \times 25 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$). Testing frequency " f_{test} " and stress ratio "R" were chosen to 10Hz and 0.1. The maximum heating of the samples did not exceed 7°C .

With the "non-penetration" falling weight impact test [31], the material can be loaded with single or multiple impacts until penetration occurs. The impact energy can be easily adjusted by varying the drop height or the drop weight. The impact testing equipment was developed according to DIN 53443 and DIN 53373. The impact force is measured with a piezoelectric sensor right behind the impactor tip. The deflection (movement of the impactor) is measured by a position sensitive detector. Impact force history and deflection are recorded and evaluated by a personal computer. If impact force is plotted against deflection, a non-penetration impact results in an open hysteresis loop defined as loss energy. The area under the hysteresis-loop is defined as strain energy. The ratio between loss and strain energy is defined as damping-index. Five samples with the dimension $60 \times 60 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$ were tested.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The increased characteristic values caused by the MAH-PP coupling agent (Figure 1) are mainly based [13,33] on a reduction of fiber pull-outs and less fiber-matrix debondings, which would lead to e.g. micropores in the interface [33]. The improved fiber-matrix interface leads to a lowering of the critical fiber length for a most effective stress transfer and because of that to a higher composite strength [33].

Figure 1 demonstrates that, the reinforcing effect and with this the flexural strength of the composite, increases, as a result of the improved force transfer from matrix to fiber [30], caused by the improved fiber-matrix adhesion. In comparison to the investigations of Karmaker et al. [30], where jute-fibers with an average fiber length of 2mm were used to reinforce polypropylene, and to the investigations of Felix et al. [29] at PP reinforced with filter paper, this investigations found an increase of flexural strength, through the higher fiber length, with increasing fiber content at jute reinforced PP even without an application of a coupling agent.

Figure 1: Influence of jute-fiber content and surface treatment on the flexural strength of jute-PP-composites

The investigations made by Mieck et al. [27] on PP reinforced with flax fibers (green flax ribbons, comb ribbon: 4.5 ktex) seem to be comparable to the here made investigations concerning the fiber length. Tensile strength of the composites is influenced similarly by the fiber content as it can be seen in figure 1. The values for flexural strength do not differ distinctly between modified and unmodified flax-PP composites up to a fiber content of about 10 vol.-%. Shear strength of the unmodified composites even decreases, after a maximum at 15% fiber content, caused by a gliding of the interface.

The improved fiber-matrix adhesion of the modified jute-polypropylene composites leads (figure 2) at comparable fiber contents to a distinctly higher dynamic strength, which is the stress at fracture measured in the load increasing test. Progress of damage (i.e. the cumulative loss-energy becomes a nonlinear function with an increasing number of load cycles [14,31]) at unmodified jute-PP composites is nearly independent of the fiber content, which results in independent maximal stresses.

Figure 2: Influence of jute-fiber content and surface treatment on the cumulated loss energy of jute-PP-composites (test frequency = 10 Hz, R = 0.1)

It is only the improved fiber-matrix adhesion, caused by the MAH-PP coupling agent and the thereby improved force transfer, which reduces the progress of damage with increasing fiber content and leads to an increasing dynamic strength.

Figure 3: Influence of fiber content on the specific damping capacity (Λ_{SDC}) of MAH-PP-modified jute-PP-composites (test frequency = 10 Hz, R = 0.1, 10^4 number of cycles/stress levels)

Contrastingly to untreated jute-polypropylene composites, an 40%-increase of dynamic strength, at comparable fiber contents (ca. 40 vol.-%), is attained through the usage of the coupling agent. Our investigations showed furthermore (figure 3 and 4) that the damage of the jute-PP composites (modified as well as unmodified ones) does not occur spontaneously, but occurs continuously with the increasing stress. Whereby the limit stress i.e. the over proportional increase of the damping (Λ_{SDC}) [10], is moved to higher stresses (exemplarily shown for jute-PP composites modified with MAH-PP).

Figure 4: Influence of surface treatment on the specific damping capacity (Λ_{SDC}) of jute-PP composites (test frequency = 10 Hz, R = 0.1, 10^4 number of cycles/stress levels)

The damage of the composites, modified with MAH-PP, starts at distinct higher upper stress values, which were for about 20 N/mm^2 (figure 4). Whereas the unmodified jute-PP composites already show a remarkable increasing damping at the starting values of the upper stress, which was 10 N/mm^2 .

Figure 5: Influence of fiber treatment and number of impacts on the damping-index of jute-PP-Composites (impact drop height = 0.2 m, impact weight = 0,75 kg, fiber content = 36 vol.-%)

Figure 5 shows that the damping-index responds sensitively to change in fiber-matrix adhesion. At the first impact the damping ratio, i.e. damping of untreated to treated composites, is about 1.6. At the first impact, the (cumulated) loss-energy is only slightly higher for the specimens with untreated fibers (figure 6). The different slopes of the cumulated impact loss-energy curves show that due to fiber-matrix debonding more energy is dissipated by the specimen without treatment when they are subjected to repeated impact.

Figure 6: Influence of fiber treatment and number of impacts on the cumulated loss-energy of Jute-PP-Composites (impact drop height = 0.2 m, impact weight = 0,75 kg, fiber content = 36 vol.-%)

CONCLUSION

Distinct risings of the characteristic values of jute-polypropylene composites were attained with the application of MAH-PP copolymers. Flexural strength was increased for 40%, a 40%-increase was also measured for the dynamic strength in the load increasing test.

The improved fiber-matrix adhesion is caused by the chemical bonds between fiber and matrix which were provided by the coupling agent. With this, the force transfer from matrix to fiber is improved which leads to an improved reinforcing effect than in unmodified composites.

The improved fiber-matrix adhesion led to a higher damage resistance at cyclic-dynamic loadings. This was to be observed by a shift of the beginning damage towards higher maximal stresses and by a slower progress of damage with increasing load cycles respectively max. stresses. The tested composites without coupling agent independently of the fiber content (21 vol.-% to 37 vol.-%) showed a nearly identical behaviour towards constant values for the dynamic strength. With the application of MAH-PP coupling agent it was possible to reduce, with increased fiber contents, the progress of damage and with this to attain an increasing dynamic strength.

The improved fiber-matrix adhesion led to a decrease in damping-index and (cululated) loss-energy at impact loadings.

REFERENCES

1. J. Gassan, A.K. Bledzki, *Angew. Makromole. Chem.* 236, 129 (1996)
2. A.K. Bledzki, S. Reihmane, J. Gassan ; *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 59, 1329 (1996)
3. N.N., Technical Information about Vestolen® P 6000F, 1994
4. D.Maldas, B.V. Kokta, R.G. Raj, C. Daneault, *Polymer* 29, 1255 (1988)
5. D.S. Varma, M. Varma, I.K. Varma, *Text. Res. Inst.* 54, 821 (1984)
6. P. Zadorecki, P. Flodin, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 31, 1699 (1986)
7. J. Gassan, A.K. Bledzki, 7th Interational Techtexsil Symposium, June 19 - 21, 1995 Frankfurt (Germany)
8. D. Maldas, B.V. Kokta, C. Daneault, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 37, 751 (1989)
9. D. Maldas, B.V. Kokta, C. Daneault, *J. Vinyl Technol.* 11 (2), 90 (1989)
10. W. Janzen, Zum Versagens- und Bruchverhalten von Kurzglasfaser-Thermoplasten, Ph.D-thesis at the University of Kassel, Institut für Werkstofftechnik, Kassel 1989
11. P. Zadorecki, T. Rönnhult, *J. Polym. Sci. Part A Polym. Chem.* 24, 737 (1986)
12. M.H. Schneider, K.I. Brebner, *Wood Sci. Technol.* 19, 67 (1985)
13. J. Kuruvilla, Th. Sabu, C. Pavithran, *Comp. Sci. Techn.* 53, 99 (1995)
14. A.K. Bledzki, J. Gassan, K. Kurek, *Experimental Mechanics*, in press
15. S.C.O. Ugbole, *Text. Inst.* 20 (4), 1 (1990)
16. J.I. Kroschwitz, *Polymers: Fibers and Textiles*, Wiley, New York, 1990
17. S.H. Zeronian, H. Kawabata, K.W. Alger, *Text. Res. Inst.* 60 (3), 179 (1990)
18. M.A. Semsazadeh, *Polym. Comp.* 7 (1), 23 (1986)
19. E.T.N. Bisanda, M.P. Ansell, *Comp. Sci. Technol.* 41, 165 (1991)

20. P.K.Ray, A.C.Chakravarty, S.B. Bandyopadhyay, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 20, 1765 (1976)
21. A.N. Shan, S.C. Lekkard, *Fibre Sci. Technol.* 15, 41 (1981)
22. L. Hua, P. Flodin, T. Rönnhult, *Polym. Comp.* 8 (3), 203 (1987)
23. L. Hua, P. Zadorecki, P. Flodin, *Polym. Comp.* 8 (3), 199 (1987)
24. T. Sterzynski, B. Triki, S. Zelazny, *Polimery* 40 (7/8), 468 (1995)
25. K.-P. Mieck, A. Nechwatal, C. Knobelsdorf, *Angew. Makromole.Chem.* 224, 73 (1995)
26. B.V. Kokta, R.G. Raj, C. Daneault, *Polym.-Plast.Technol.Eng.* 28 (3), 247 (1989)
27. K.-P. Mieck, A. Nechwatal, C. Knobelsdorf, *Angew. Makromole.Chem.* 225, 37 (1995)
28. M. Avella, C. Bozzi, R. dell'Ebra, B. Focher, A. Marzetti, E. Martuscelli, *Angew. Makromole.Chem.* 233, 149 (1995)
29. J. Felix, P. Gatenholm; *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 42, 609 (1991)
30. A. Karmaker, J. Schneider, *J. Mater.Sci.Letters* 15, 201 (1996)
31. A.K. Bledzki, K. Kurek, G. Wacker, J. Gassan, *Materialprüfung* 37, 360 (1995)
32. B. Lazan, Damping of Materials and Membrans in Structural Mechanics, Pergamon Press (1968)
33. S. Dong, S. Sapiaha, H.P. Schreiber, *Polym. Eng. Sci.* 33, 343 (1993)

Notation

R	Stress ratio
Λ_{SDC}	Specific damping capacity
σ_{flex}	Flexural strength
ϕ	Fiber content